

Secular shift of the magnetic dip pole and its consequences for auroral boundaries: an update (PoleMotion 2)

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1. Introduction

During the last decades, the Earth's northern magnetic dip pole has moved rapidly across the Arctic. The dip pole marks the location where the local magnetic field is vertical, and its location is to a large extent determined by two patches of intense magnetic field located at the Core–Mantle Boundary under Canada and Siberia. A strengthening of the Siberian patch and a weakening of the Canadian patch have caused the dip pole to move towards Siberia (Livermore et al. 2020). This motion raises the question of to what extent the auroral oval shifts in response to such changes in the geomagnetic field. Earlier studies suggested minimal effects (Tsyganenko 2019), while more recent results indicate a possible poleward motion of the aurora (Zossi et al. 2020, 2021).

Svalbard, with its long time series of both magnetic field and auroral observations, is well suited to study these changes. In the original report, we investigated whether long-term variations in the geomagnetic field influence auroral activity over Svalbard, and documented gradual changes in the local magnetic field. Initial results from this study were presented in the SIOS report 2024 (Haaland et al. 2025), hereafter referred to as PoleMotion. This update expands the observational record by adding a year's worth of satellite data from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), incorporating European Incoherent Scatter (EISCAT) radar observations of dayside aurora, and refining the methodology for automatically detecting aurora in the EISCAT data.

2. The state of the magnetic field changes and auroral changes

2.1. Secular variations in the magnetic field in Svalbard: Updated observations

Regular magnetic field measurements from the Hornsund observatory in Svalbard were presented in Haaland et al. (2025). In this update, we extend the analysis by adding measurements from additional magnetometer stations across the Svalbard archipelago: Longyearbyen, Ny-Ålesund, and Hopen. Figure 1 shows the location of these magnetometer stations, and Figure 2 shows the evolution of the magnetic field measured at the additional stations, along with the measurements from Hornsund. Data from the additional stations confirm the same pattern identified in last year's report: a steady clockwise rotation of the horizontal field components (B_x , B_y), indicating an accumulated rotation of about 10° over the last decades. Inclination and declination angles are not shown in the figure, but can be calculated as $I = \arctan\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2}}\right)$ and $D = \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right)$. For example, from 1995 to 2025, the declination angle changed by $+9.74^\circ$ and the inclination angle changed by 0.49° . At the same time, both the

vertical component (B_z) and the total field strength (B_{tot}) have increased. While this may seem counter to the global decline of Earth's dipole moment (Koochak and Fraser-Smith 2017), the trend is consistent with the migrating pole gradually approaching Svalbard's position. The extended

Figure 1: Map showing the location of the four magnetometer stations used in this update: Ny-Ålesund (NAL), Longyearbyen (LYR), Hornsund (HOR), and Hopen (HOP).

analysis of auroral boundary variations is conducted in the context of these continued secular changes in Svalbard's magnetic field environment.

2.2. Secular variation in the auroral oval location: Update

Using the same methodology as in PoleMotion, we have extended our satellite-based auroral boundary detection to August 2025. The approach continues to rely on field-aligned electron flux measurements from the Medium Energy Proton and Electron Detector (MEPED) onboard multiple NOAA and MetOp satellites to identify sharp transitions that serve as proxies for auroral boundaries.

Our automated boundary detection algorithm has now processed over 750,000 boundary crossings in the extended 27-year period, an increase from the 700,000+ boundaries identified in the previous analysis. As in PoleMotion, there is substantial variability in boundary positions due to space weather dynamics operating across timescales from minutes to days, with equatorward displacement of boundaries during enhanced solar wind conditions, and a poleward contraction under geomagnetically quiet conditions.

To investigate secular changes in position of the auroral oval over Svalbard, we applied the same geographic filtering approach as in PoleMotion, selecting all valid boundaries detected within the

Figure 2: Evolution of the magnetic field in different magnetometers: Ny-Ålesund (NAL in black), Longyearbyen (LYR in red), Hornsund (HOR in blue), and Hopen (HOP in green) over the last few decades. Top to bottom panels: Bx (north-south component), By (eastward component), Bz (vertical down), and Btot (total magnitude). The vertical component (Bz), larger than the horizontal components (Bx, By), is almost vertical, and it has increased over the last decades. Short-time variations can be ignored as these result from effects other than the secular changes of interest for this study.

1°-31° geographic longitude sector. Boundaries detected during geomagnetically disturbed conditions ($K_p > 2+$) were excluded to minimise space weather contamination and the underlying secular signal from both the 11-year solar cycle and 27-day solar rotation effects.

The extended time series, now spanning 1998 through August 2025, reinforces the secular equatorward displacement identified in our previous analysis and shown in Figure 4 of Haaland et al. (2025). Linear regression analysis reveals a persistent, albeit gradual, southward migration of both boundary types throughout the observation period.

The additional year of observations strengthens the statistical significance of the detected trends while maintaining the same fundamental pattern. Both the poleward and equatorward boundaries still show a systematic equatorward motion, consistent with the hypothesis that the auroral oval is responding to the ongoing northward drift of Earth's magnetic dip pole. The secular change remains modest in amplitude compared to the substantial variability imposed by space weather effects, which continue to dominate the year-to-year fluctuations visible in the time series.

These updated results remain consistent with the interpretation that Earth's changing internal magnetic field configuration is exerting a measurable, long-term influence on auroral boundary positions, superimposed upon the much larger amplitude variations driven by solar wind-magnetosphere interactions.

2.3. Updated methodology for EISCAT auroral boundary detection

In our earlier report (Haaland et al. 2025), auroral boundaries were identified by visually inspecting electron density profiles around 110 km altitude for sharp gradients. While this method gave a useful first-order estimate of auroral occurrence, it lacked formal thresholds, could not easily be automated, and was not straightforward to benchmark against multiple events. In the present update, we refined

the approach by introducing a systematic detection scheme that integrates both physical constraints on EISCAT parameters and automated rules. This allows us to delineate auroral boundaries in the E and F regions with greater consistency, and to take a step toward a reproducible and operational methodology.

The analysis began with the selection of events. Eight auroral intervals were identified on both the dayside and the nightside between 2000 and 2023, using a pre-determined event list together with the Madrigal EISCAT database. Background intervals were also included for reference. For each case, the relevant ionospheric altitude was chosen according to local time: F-region observations near 250 km were used on the dayside (09-15 Magnetic Local Time (MLT)), whereas E-region observations near 110 km were selected for nightside conditions (18-7 MLT). An example of a selected dayside and a nightside event can be seen in Figure 3. The EISCAT measurements were then cleaned. Data were excluded if the relative error in electron density (D_{N_e}) exceeded half of the electron density (N_e), if N_e was lower than 10^8 m^{-3} or higher than 10^{13} m^{-3} , or if electron temperature lay outside the physically reasonable range of 0–10,000 K.

A further improvement over last year's work was the construction of a dedicated table that merges EISCAT observations with solar wind and geomagnetic indices. From the Madrigal EISCAT files, we extracted electron density (N_e), electron temperature (T_e), and associated uncertainties, to combine these with the 1-minute OMNI data set of solar wind data (King and Papitashvili 2005). The resulting product, a table stored in the Magnetic Pulsations and Transients (MAPAT) database, provides a continuous multi-year time series that can be queried directly. The same physical filters applied during event cleaning – error consistency, density thresholds, and valid T_e limits – were also imposed at the database level. This new data resource, which did not exist at the time of the earlier study, provides a more uniform examination of the auroral boundaries across decades of observations, while also allowing cross-referencing with geomagnetic activity indices such

Figure 3: Example of identified aurora on the dayside (left) and nightside (right).

as the Disturbance Storm Time (Dst) index. It also enables automated, large-scale testing of detection rules, moving beyond the purely case-study-based approach used previously.

Thresholds for auroral detection were then derived from the selected events. By comparing the average minima and maxima of both T_e and N_e across the 16 auroral and background cases, we established ranges that define whether a given data point belongs to an auroral boundary or not. To increase robustness, additional requirements were introduced: candidate auroral events must be separated by at least 5 minutes, have a duration of at least three consecutive points (about 3 minutes), and coincide with negative Dst values sustained for three or more samples. Both dayside and nightside thresholds were tested against the extreme values (“min-of-min” and “max-of-max”) across the dataset to confirm stability.

The implementation of these rules was carried out in a modular Python script. The detection pipeline proceeds in several stages. First, each individual measurement is checked against the day/night thresholds for T_e and N_e . Consecutive points satisfying the criteria are then grouped into candidate events. These are subjected to post-processing checks, including the Dst and duration constraints, after which boundary validation is performed by a rolling-average peak-detection

routine. This final step ensures that the resulting events are associated with real electron density enhancements characteristic of auroral boundaries. Compared to last year’s method, which relied largely on visual identification of density peaks, the new scheme combines physical parameter limits with statistical consistency checks, making it more robust and reproducible.

The updated methodology was applied to all available files, yielding statistical ranges for both electron temperature and density. On the dayside, the median minimum values for T_e and N_e were found to be over 1247 K and $3.65 \times 10^{10} \text{ m}^{-3}$, respectively. As for the nightside aurora, the median minimum N_e value was $2.79 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^{-3}$ with the median maximum value at $7.34 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-3}$, and for T_e , in this scenario, the median minimum was 2.70 K and the median maximum was 3540 K. A summary of the derived thresholds is provided in Table 1, which lists the parameter ranges separately for dayside (250 km) and nightside (110 km) conditions. The rule set includes the temperature and density thresholds as well as the requirement of sustained negative Dst values for at least 3 minutes. These criteria define the operational detection scheme that has now been implemented for the automated identification of auroral boundaries in the EISCAT dataset.

Table 1: Rule set for the EISCAT auroral boundary detection, as implemented in the updated algorithm. DST (Disturbance Storm Time) index is a geomagnetic activity index.

Parameter	Dayside (250 km)	Nightside (110 km)
Electron temperature (T_e [K])	≥ 1247	2.70 – 3540
Electron density (N_e [m^{-3}])	$\geq 3.65 \times 10^{10}$	$2.79 \times 10^9 - 7.34 \times 10^{11}$
Dst index (for ≥ 3 points)	< 0	< 0

By normalising the detected boundaries to the total observation time of each year, we obtained a boundary detection frequency. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the detection frequency over 24 years of EISCAT Svalbard data. We note a declining detection probability over time with a negative inclination of 5.1% (red dashed line). While this

trend is consistent with the remote sensing data, and may suggest that the auroral oval is shifting away from Svalbard, the results are subject to uncertainties and potential biases that require further investigation. For example, an aurora moving southwards does not necessarily mean that it falls out of range of the radar observations.

Figure 4: Frequency of the auroral boundaries (dayside and nightside) as detected in the EISCAT Svalbard radar (ESR) over the last 24 years. The dashed line shows a linear fit to the observations.

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

The primary focus of the updated chapter has been to improve the methodology for detecting auroral boundaries from the EISCAT Svalbard radar data, as well as expand the dataset by including dayside observations. The improved methodology and expanded dataset yield results consistent with the equatorward motion of the auroral oval reported in the original chapter. Further refinement of the methodology within a larger project could lead to more precise detection. This would include also testing alternative approaches, such as machine learning, to evaluate which method provides the most accurate results.

Investigating how the auroral oval responds to changes in the magnetic field, requires contributions from both the geomagnetism and the space science communities. The results from this project could facilitate further interdisciplinary collaboration by enabling comparisons between auroral observations and geomagnetic models, providing opportunities to improve both theoretical models and our understanding of auroral boundary movements. These advancements, including the development of a core auroral boundary dataset and refined detection methods, demonstrate how combining expertise from multiple disciplines contributes to enhancing our knowledge of the Space–Earth system.

4. Unanswered questions

Several questions remain unanswered. As in the past report, we do not know how the dip pole will move in the next few decades, and what consequences this will have for the auroral oval and observations. It is still unclear whether the equatorward movement of the auroral oval seen in the satellite data and the declining amount of aurora detected in EISCAT data are directly caused by the magnetic pole movement. Continuous

observations and long-term monitoring may help resolve this question. Further work is also needed to compare different methods for auroral detection in the EISCAT dataset and to identify the most reliable approach. Additionally, it remains an open question how auroral measurements from satellites and ground-based radar align with the models commonly used in geomagnetic studies.

5. Recommendations for the future

As noted in the original report (Haaland et al. 2025), ground-based datasets such as EISCAT Svalbard radar remain challenging to use due to the radar typically only running during campaigns, which often occur during specific geomagnetic conditions. To reduce potential biases in the datasets, it is recommended to establish some regularly scheduled radar runs.

Currently, this study is based on the IGRF-13 model (Alken et al. 2021) and uses the magnetic

local time (MLT). However, an improvement could be done using the Altitude Adjusted Corrected Geomagnetic (AACGM) or Apex magnetic (Richmond 1995) coordinate systems instead. The results could be compared, as AACGM and Apex both track the magnetic field along the field lines in their respective systems, which could improve the consistency of auroral boundary detections at different altitudes.

Therefore, enhancing collaboration between the geomagnetism and the space science communities should be prioritised. This could improve understanding of the Space–Earth system by allowing more direct comparison between theoretical models and auroral observations.

Finally, Svalbard hosts several optical instruments used for studying aurora. Developing automated methods to detect aurora in optical data would allow comparison with radar observations and could help refine and validate the auroral detection methodology.

6. Data availability

All data used for this study are available from public archives. Links to data sources are shown in Table

2. The Python script used in this study is available on GitHub¹.

Table 2: Overview of data sources. NOAA = National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration; IMAGE = International Monitor for Auroral Geomagnetic Effects; NASA = National Aeronautics and Space Administration; CDAWeb = Coordinated Data Analysis Web.

Dataset	Period	Data provider	URL
Space weather	1994-2024	NASA CDAWeb, USA	https://spdf.gsfc.nasa.gov/pub/data/omni/low_res_omni/
Magnetic field	1994-2001	IMAGE, Finland	https://space.fmi.fi/image/www/
Magnetic field	2002-2024	Intermagnet, UK	https://imag-data.bgs.ac.uk/GIN_V1/
EISCAT	2000-2023	Madrigal, Sweden	https://madrigal.eiscat.se/madrigal/
METOPS and POES satellite data	1998-2025	NOAA, USA	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/poes-metop-space-environment-monitor
IGRF-13 model	1900-2025	IAGA	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/international-geomagnetic-reference-field

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Information. The OMNI data were obtained from the GSFC/SPDF OMNIWeb interface². EISCAT is an international association supported by research organisations in China (CRIRP), Finland (SA), Japan (NIPR and ISEE), Norway (NFR), Sweden (VR), and the United Kingdom (UKRI). L. Bjoland was supported by the Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology through the Arctic Challenge for Sustainability II (ArCS II; JPMXD1420318865). This work was financially supported by UI/BD/153350/2022 of the

¹ <https://github.com/toni-santos/aurora-algo>

² <https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

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Northern lights over Gruvefjellet, Longyearbyen. (Photo: Hannes Brüdersdorf)

Map showing the movement of the magnetic dip pole, where the observed field is vertical (red), and the modelled geomagnetic dipole pole (blue). (Modified from chapter 1 in SESS report 2024; Map: Lindis Bjoland)

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The Earth's northern magnetic pole is moving. Extended analysis of data from four magnetometer stations across Svalbard confirms archipelago-wide magnetic field changes.
- New automated methodology using EISCAT radar data helps track how magnetic field changes shift the auroral oval above Svalbard.

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The Earth's magnetic dip pole, where the observed field is vertical, and the modelled geomagnetic dipole pole, which is roughly the centre of the auroral oval, are both moving. This leads to changes in the local magnetic field over Svalbard and can affect infrastructure and navigation. For example, runway designations at airports are periodically updated due to shifts in the magnetic orientation. As economic activity and infrastructure expand in Svalbard, understanding magnetic field evolution is increasingly important for long-term planning and operational safety.

This 2025 update builds on last year's SESS report by incorporating magnetic field data from three more stations: Longyearbyen, Ny-Ålesund, and Hopen. The new data confirm the eastward rotation and field strengthening observed at Hornsund, showing consistent magnetic changes across the archipelago.

A major advance this year is a new automated method for detecting auroral boundaries in EISCAT Svalbard radar data. This method replaces visual identification with a systematic approach based on electron temperature and density thresholds, including quality controls for consistent boundary identification and separation between dayside and nightside conditions.

With the new data, the satellite observations now span 27 years and over 750,000 auroral boundary crossings, and confirm the equatorward motion of auroral boundaries over Svalbard. The automated EISCAT analysis also confirms this trend, showing a declining frequency of auroral boundary detections. Together, these results strengthen confidence in the detected trends.

These improvements enable more systematic long-term monitoring and comparison with models. The convergence of the conclusions drawn from satellite remote sensing, ground-based radar measurements, and magnetometer networks demonstrates how integrated observational approaches yield insights impossible to achieve through individual measurement systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Establish Core Auroral Dataset:** Develop a standardised core auroral boundary dataset for long-term monitoring and comparison across different methods.
- **Enhance Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration:** Strengthen links between the geomagnetism and space science communities for improved theoretical-observational comparisons.
- **Establish Regular EISCAT Operations:** Implement scheduled radar runs to reduce biases from campaign-based operations during specific geomagnetic conditions.

Inside the magnetic observatory building in Hornsund. (Photo: Szymon Oryński, Polish Polar Station Hornsund)

Magnetic observatory in Hornsund. (Photo: Szymon Oryński, Polish Polar Station Hornsund)

Magnetic observatory in Ny-Ålesund. (Photo: Magnar Gullikstad Johnsen, Tromsø Geophysical Observatory)